

General preparation and properties of complexes: One mole of uranyl nitrate hexahydrate solution in dry acetone was made to react with excess of the Schiff base. The complex thus formed, was filtered, washed free from the ligand using petroleum ether and dried at 50°.

All the complexes are crystalline. They are highly coloured. They are soluble in most of the common organic solvents. They are quite stable upto 150° but at higher temperatures they decompose.

Analysis: Uranium was estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method¹⁵. The analytical results are indicated in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Physical and analytical data of Uranium(VI) Complexes

S. No.	Schiff bases used	Empirical formulae	Colour	% of Uranium		% of Nitrogen		Decompn. temp.
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1.	I	$UO_2(C_{11}H_{12}NO)_2$	Lemon yellow	38.15	38.39	4.35	4.50	> 166°
2.	II	$UO_2(C_{12}H_{15}NO)_2$	Orange	35.50	36.70	4.10	4.32	> 118°
3.	III	$UO_2(C_{11}H_{11}ClNO)_2$	Reddish yellow	33.40	34.61	4.05	4.08	> 155°
4.	IV	$UO_2(C_{12}H_{15}NO_2)_2$	Reddish brown	34.10	35.50	4.28	4.18	> 148°
5.	V	$UO_2(C_{13}H_{20}N_2O_2)_2$	Canary yellow	46.92	47.03	5.48	5.53	> 188°
6.	VI	$UO_2(C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_4)_2$	Brick red	38.45	38.64	4.64	4.54	> 240°

The infrared spectra of the complexes in nujol mull were obtained with Perkin-Elmer 472.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristic vibrations in the I.R. spectra of the complexes are listed in Table 2, along with their pertinent assignments. A weak band around 2940 cm^{-1} in all the complexes is assigned to CH stretching mode. Ueno and Martell¹⁶ have assigned C = N stretching vibration in case of acetylacetone ethylene diamine and salicylidene ethylene-diamine to the 1600–1556 cm^{-1} region. The strong band found in the complexes under investigation in 1685–1600 cm^{-1} region is assigned to C = N stretching vibrations. The shift towards the lower frequency suggests that the coordination has taken place through the nitrogen of the azomethine group and consequently the band order of carbon to nitrogen link is decreased. The three high intensity bands around 1600–1460 cm^{-1} are attributed to C = C stretching vibrations in view of the assignments made by Teyssie *et al.*¹⁷.

The C–O stretching mode of the phenolimine form of the Schiff bases usually found around 1280 cm^{-1} in the ligands¹⁸ is found in the region between 1370–1335 cm^{-1} in the complexes. This shift towards higher frequency suggests the M–O bond formation. Similar observations were made by Martell *et al.*¹⁶ in the case of Schiff base complexes with transition metals.

TABLE 2

Infrared frequencies (cm⁻¹) of Complexes and their probable assignments^a

1	2	3	4	5	6	Assignments
2940 Br	2940	2960	2960	2980	2940	ν CH
1595 S	1590	1590	1585	1600	1590	ν C=N
1580 S	1570	1575	1545	1570 W	1550	
1525	1510	1510	1510	1520 W		ν C=C
1460	1480	1465	1475	1465 W	1460	
1370 S	1375	1370	1370	1380	1370 S	
1360 Sh		1360	1365	1370	Br	ν C-O
1320 Sh		1325	1320	1330	1335 W	
945	935	940	950	930	965 D	ν U=O
935	865	845	840	855	925	
					890	
					825	

a : *abbreviations* : S = sharp, Sh = shoulder, Br = Broad, W = Weak, D = Doublet.

Uranyl ion gives three vibrations in the following regions : Two bands around 950–800 cm⁻¹ (ν_3 & ν_1) and the third one around 210 cm⁻¹ (ν_2). All the three bands are Raman and infra red active if the uranyl ion is non-linear. On the contrary two bands (ν_2 & ν_3) are infra red active and ν_1 band is Raman active (^{9,20} if uranyl ion is linear. In the complexes under investigation there is a strong band in the region 880–825 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to ν_1 vibration. The other band which is equally strong in the region 930–965 cm⁻¹ may be due to ν_3 vibrations. However, it cannot be conclusively said that the band observed around 950 cm⁻¹ is due to symmetric stretching of ν_3 only, as the strong skeletal vibrations which occur in the same region usually interfere with the ν_3 vibrations. It is likely that there is a distortion from the linearity because of the strong local field due to the ligand environment.

In acetylaceton benzidine uranium(VI) complexes two intense bands at 965 and 925 cm⁻¹ and two more at 890 and 825 cm⁻¹ are found which are very similar with the known vanadyl Schiff base complexes²⁰. A dimeric structure has been proposed for the complexes as the monomeric structure is not possible on steric grounds. The complexes hitherto reported are of dimeric nature only.

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